

**SOCIAL ASSESSMENT OF KHANDI VILLAGE AT MAVAL TAHSIL IN
PUNE DISTRICT, (M.S.), INDIA.**

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1. Introduction:

The village is very small unit of human settlement. The village is also one of the good examples of stage cultural development of man on the surface of the earth. Geographers role is to understand this stage of cultural development and its relationship with natural environment.

The village survey provides the primary data regarding different aspects of life style of man in the village. Environment has direct impact on village culture. Natural phenomenon directly governs the village setup. Therefore it is very important to study natural phenomenon along with human beings.

The government of India and government of Maharashtra continuously try to develop the villages, as the 3/4th of the Indian population lives in this habitat. Government introduces May schemes for people's welfare. Urban people have least contact with villagers therefore it is necessary to visit the village to see the percolation extent of government. Plans and schemes to find out the problem and finally to conclude the suggestion.

The geographical set up mostly includes the geographical location. Physiography, climate and the vegetation aspects. The cultural, social and economical environment has always been influenced by the geographical condition or the place. The geo-graphical environment includes the availability of the natural resources at a particular place. Natural resources are many things found to man & also useful to man in the natural environment.

2. Aims & Objective of Study:

- To Study the Educational Status of the Khandi Village.
- To study caste status of the Khandi Village.
- To study Religion status of the Khandi Village.
- To study the available Facilities of Khandi Village.

3. Methodology: Actually it is the first stage study while preparing the village survey report possibly there may be different views on the aspect of selection of study area for the village survey report.

3.1. Primary data:

Primary data required for this paper has been collected by conducting interviews, discussion, and prepare questionnaire.

3.2. Secondary data:

Secondary data required for this paper has been collected by reviewing articles, books, and also from websites.

3.3. Laboratory Component:

Ms-excel, Graphs, Pie-Chart.

4. Geographical location of Khandi Village:

The village Khandi is located on the left bank of Thokarwadi dam. The approach road to village Khandi is 72 KM westward from pimpri, pune on old NH4 from the Kane phata. From Kane phata one should have go to 25 KM Southward to village Khandi. This road is unmetalled road. The village Khandi is located at 18° 52' 626 North latitude to 73° 31' 732" East longitude in the Tehasil Maval of Pune district.

The village is located exactly at south west slope of river Thokarwadi dam. Therefore at north east side the slope height decreases towards Thkalewadi Dam. In the northwest side of Khandi water divided between Thokarwadi dam. The northwest geographical area of the village covers major part of this hilly water divider between both the rivers. Few small streams originated from this water

divider drains. Northward to Thokarwadi Dam. Geographically village is foot of the hill and near from Thokarwadi Dam. As a result of drainage and relief the depth of the soil at the top of water divide is $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 M at many places. The water divide shows the igneous rock. The terraces at the bottom of right bank slope of river.

5. Physiography:

The village is located at the height 650m meter above sea level. The height of Khandi and surround area ranges above sea level. The area lies on a gentle southeasterly sloping plateau to the east of the western Ghats, at levels between 580 m to 610 m above the mean sea level. On this plateau stand the lofty ridges which run west to east or northwest to south-east with successive lower heights towards east or south-east respectively, in the southern part of the area the Bhatras hill range rises from $< 3621'$ level (1104 M) and after 30 km long stretch towards east descends to small hillocks near Dehu road Railway Station.

6. Drainage:

Khandi is situated near by Thokarwadi dam, which has eastern side of sahyadri mountain ranges. There are many tributaries flowing towards the Thokarwadi dam.

7. Climate:

As the village is part of Maval Tehasil in pune district it experience heavy rainfall in the monsoon season. The area normally receives average annual rainfall between 160 CM to 240 CM. The area experience cold winter with the annual temperature range between 19°c to 24°c . The area experience hot summer with average temperature range between 31°c to 42°c . The area is example of typical tropical monsoon climatic type.

8. Vegetation:

Vegetation is reflection annual of rainfall, soil cover status, physiographic &

climate of the area. The village has northwest hilly region totally about reserved forest land. The forest includes trees like bamboo, people tree, neem, and eucalyptus. Forest type is tropical deciduous type. Forest has many

Specious trees like Nilgiri, Neem and banyans are planted by the forest department. The villagers have planted some trees in front of their houses.

9. Social Status of Khandi Village:

The objective of the social study of the village is to examine the population, standard of living, facilities available in the village. Trade, Transport and settlement, Hospital, School etc.

Following parameters will consider for under-standing social structure.

9.1. Standard of living:

The standard of living in KHANDI is medium to low. Most of the people in the village are workers. Some people are working in their own firm. A large number of people working in small piece of land, which they have inherited or they work in other field. Some of them migrate to cities for work or education purpose. The service man families have slightly upgraded and medium standard of living.

9.2. Food habit:

On an average the people consume simple meal. The daily meal consists of Roti (Bhakari), Pulses, rice, vegetable & non-veg also. Bhakari and rice are main items in the life villager's food. As there is less development of irrigation, the villagers do not grow many vegetables in their farm. So they have to depend on the market for their daily requirement of vegetables.

Food Habits	No of House Holder	Percentage (%)
Veg.	102	29.91
Mixed	239	70.09
Total	341	99.90

Table No. 01: Food Habits of Khandi Village

Figure No. 01: Food habits in Khandi village

In Khandi, 29.91% families are vegetarian and 70.09% families use mix type of food in their daily use.

9.3. Facilities available in the Village:

Table No. 02: Available Facilities in the Village

No	Facilities	Yes/ No
1	Pre-Primary School	Yes
2	Primary School	Yes
3	Secondary School	No
4	Provisional Store	Yes
5	Post Office	No
6	Mosque	No
7	Temple	Yes
8	Water tank	Yes
9	Primary Rural Hospital	Yes
10	Hotel	No
11	Ration shop	No
12	Bank	No
13	Co-Operative Society	No

9.3.1. Communication:

There are number of mobile connections, telephone connections are available some houses in this village. Television, internet facilities, Radio, communication facilities are available in some houses.

9.3.2. Medical Facilities:

Medical facilities are available in the village. There is Primary Government Health Center also available in Khandi. For medical emergencies villagers have to run Pune.

9.3.3. Market:

The main market is located in Vadgaon Maval, where the farmer came to sell their yield and sometimes they even sell it in Pune market. In Khandi weekly market is not observed but, there is weekly vegetable and yield van comes in that village on every Thursday.

9.3.4. Drinking Water:

Government and private taps are available in this village for the purpose of drinking Water as well as a water tank also available in the village Khandi.

9.3.5. Transportation:

There are both facilities metalled, unmetalled roads and also unmetalled road are outside of the village. Metalled roads meet Pune-Mumbai National Highway at Kanhephata. The villages connected to the settlement of Talegaon & Lonawala by road as well as Pune but inside village roads are found in a bad condition. There are kaccha roads which are not motor able in rainy season linking the Wadis. Commonly used means of transport is bullock Cart, tractors, through some even report to bicycle, motors & head loads for some purpose.

9.3.6. Education:

Education is necessary for the development of every sphere of human activity. It is the most important tools for income of household, health, hygiene and standard of living. The Village has an Anganwadi, a primary school name as Zillah

Perished Primary School serves the Purpose of primary education.

Table No.03: Educational Status of Khandi Village

Educational Class	Male	Female
0-1	14	9
2-5	56	55
6-10	95	64
>11	34	20
Total	199	148

Figure No. 02: Educational Status of Khandi Village

Above table shows the 6th to 10th class population is more & above 11th class population is less. It indicates that the area of Khandi is less educated.

9.3.7. Language:

Generally all the people use talk in Marathi in all surveyed families. Their mother tongue Is Marathi. They use this language while talking within them. Marathi language is the mother tongue in all surveyed families.

9.3.8. Culture:

As a village of Maharashtra this village KHANDI also shows custom and culture Peculiar to the village. The village gaathan has a Vitthal-Rukmai temple. There were various groups such as Bhajanimandal, TarunMandal, Dhol-Tasha Mandal etc. The festivals like Mhasoba yatra, Ganapati, Navaratra are celebrated in the village. In the April month annual festival is celebrated.

Religion & Cast status

9.3.9. Religion & Cast status:

Religion is an organized collection of beliefs, culture systems, and world views that relate humanity to an order of existence. Many religions have narratives, symbols, and sacred histories that are intended to explain the meaning of life and/or to explain the origin of life or the Universe. From their beliefs about the cosmos and human nature, people derive morality, ethics, religious laws or a preferred lifestyle. According to some estimates, there are roughly 4200 religious in the world.

Table No. 04: Religious Status of Khandi Village.

Religion	No. of people	Percentage
Hindu	255	100
Muslim	-	-
Christi	-	-
Total	255	100

Figure No. 03: Religion Status of Khandi Village

The hindus constitute the majority community in khandi village. The Hindus comprised 100% of the total population in khandi village.

Table No. 05: Cast Status of Khandi Village.

Cast	No. of people	Percentage
Open	37	27.82
ST	85	63.91
SC	10	7.52
VJNT	1	0.76
OBC	-	-
Total	133	100.01

Figure No. 04: Cast Status of Khandi Village

As per details from the study area the ST category constitute the majority community in study area & it has 85 (63.91%). After the ST category second majority community has other open category. It has 27.82% schedule cast and VJNT has 7.52% and 0.76% respectively

10. Conclusion:

Khandi Village is near from pune and pimpri chinchwad municipal corporation but khandi village is under development, educational facilities, transport facilities, hospital facilities, market facility are not enough for the people of the Khandi Village

Hence there is no higher educated people and observe low level of the standard of living. Most of the people engaged in the agriculture.

- Village Khandi has ideal locality on the bank of Thokarwadi Dam snorthern side and the agricultural land at its southern side. This situation provides better prospectus in agriculture development.
- The village is compactly populated. The people experienced medium to poor Socio-Economic conditions.
- There is no proper road and public transport facility in the village. This village face number of problems regarding internal road are narrow as well as pore drainage. Waste water is drained along the road.
- People either go personal vehicles or private transport (jeep, Matador.) There are number of two-wheelers and four wheelers in the entire village.
- The facilities amenities are not developed to a satisfactory level. The amenities available in the village are Electricity, Road, and Primary Schools etc.

11. References:

Director of village census of Maharashtra – pune district- 2014.

Land use register of Khandi.

www.consusindia.net.

Population Geography –R. C. Chandra.